

RSS-Based DoA Estimation with ESPAR Antennas Using Reduced Number of Radiation Patterns

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Abstract—In this letter, we investigate how direction-of-arrival (DoA) estimation algorithms, which are designed for electronically steerable parasitic array radiator (ESPAR) antennas and rely solely on received signal strength (RSS) values recorded at antenna's output port, will perform when limited number of radiation patterns will be used. To this end we have inspected two algorithms, which are easily applicable in WSN nodes having simple and inexpensive transceivers and provide accurate results. Measurements conducted using a fabricated ESPAR antenna indicate that it is possible to limit the number of radiation patterns in DoA estimation procedure and still keep the original accuracy. Hence, depending on application, the time required for DoA estimation in WSN nodes using ESPAR antennas can be reduced from 50% up to 75%.

Index Terms—Switched-beam antenna, electronically steerable parasitic array radiator (ESPAR) antenna, direction-of-arrival (DoA), received signal strength (RSS), wireless sensor network (WSN).

I. INTRODUCTION

Direction-of-Arrival (DoA) estimation is a technique that allows one to determine directions of unknown radio frequency (RF) signals impinging the antenna and it is commonly used to enhance capabilities of wireless communication systems [1]. To provide accurate results, it usually relies on digital beamforming technique applied to signals received by antenna arrays [2], therefore requires a number of digital signal processing (DSP) units. However, due to high costs and energy consumption, such an approach have very limited applicability in wireless sensor network (WSN) nodes, which require much simpler and more energy efficient approach [3].

To overcome the above limitations, one can involve electronically steerable parasitic array radiator (ESPAR) antenna that require only one processing unit for DoA estimation [2]. In such antennas, an active element placed in the center of the antenna is surrounded by a number of passive elements connected to variable reactances [4]. It has been shown, that it is possible to create a directional radiation pattern and rotate it by changing values of the reactances electronically [5], [6]. As a consequence, by recording signal samples at the output port, while rotating the main directional beam around the antenna, one can estimate DoA of an unknown signal impinging the antenna [5]-[7].

Recently proposed ESPAR antenna concepts that can easily be integrated with WSN nodes rely on simplified beam steering concept, in which parasitic elements are connected to impedances close to open or short circuit via RF switches [6], [7]. By using such antennas, one can estimate DoA with 2° precision employing power pattern cross-correlation (PPCC) algorithm, first introduced in [5], that relies on received signal strength (RSS) values recorded at the output port [8]. However, such simplification in beam forming and beam steering process require special ESPAR antenna designs having the lowest possible side lobe level (SLL) [9]. As a result, in order to have DoA estimation accuracy at the acceptable level, one has to use ESPAR antennas having twelve passive elements and, in consequence, also the same number of directional main beams in PPCC algorithm.

For DoA estimation of BPSK test signals in the horizontal plane with 2° precision and 0.612° root-mean-square (RMS) error, one has to record 10 snapshots of the signal for each of the twelve radiation patterns, when signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is equal to 20 dB. It gives 120 snapshots that has to be recorded during the whole procedure and this number may easily rise for higher noise levels, which may cause negative effects in WSN applications requiring fast reaction times, like localization of mobile WSN nodes [10]-[12].

In this paper, we investigate the possibilities of using reduced number of radiation patterns in DoA estimation relying on ESPAR antennas having twelve passive elements. To this end, we have inspected two algorithms, which are easily applicable in WSN nodes having simple and inexpensive transceivers, namely deterministic PPCC and recently introduced machine learning-based method [13] that require only RSS information recorded at the antenna output port. In this paper, we show, that it is possible to reduce the number of radiation patterns in RSS-based DoA estimation and still provide acceptable results that may be applicable in practical WSN applications.

II. ESPAR ANTENNA WITH SIMPLIFIED BEAM STEERING

To be easily integrated with simple WSN nodes, ESPAR antenna, proposed in [6], [7], has a single active monopole fed by an SMA connector that can be connected to WSN node radio frequency (RF) transceiver's output and is surrounded by twelve passive elements, which can be individually

shortened to the ground or opened by corresponding single-pole, double-throw (SPDT) switches connected to the elements' ends at the bottom layer of the structure. Such ESPAR antenna optimized to work at 2.484 GHz and then fabricated using inexpensive FR4 laminate is presented in Fig. 1.

Because the SPDT switches are connected to WSN node's microcontroller digital input output (DIO) ports, the antenna's radiation pattern can easily be set via a corresponding steering vector $V = [v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{12}]$ within the microcontroller memory, in which v_n set to 0 means that a corresponding n -th parasitic element is connected to the ground and opened for $v_n = 1$. Therefore, by setting a steering vector $V_{max}^1 = [1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]$, a directional main beam having 3 dB beamwidth that equals to 73.2° in horizontal direction with the maximum for $\theta_{max}^1 = 61^\circ$ and $\varphi_{max}^1 = 90^\circ$ (aligned with y axis) will be created [7]. Additionally, by applying a circular shift to V_{max}^1 , it is possible to produce twelve different steering vectors $\{V_{max}^1, V_{max}^2, \dots, V_{max}^{12}\}$ for horizontal directions $\{\varphi_{max}^1 = 90^\circ, \varphi_{max}^2 = 120^\circ, \dots, \varphi_{max}^{12} = 60^\circ\}$, in which the main beam is shifted by the multiple of 30° [7], [8]. By recording received packets for all twelve directional main beams and calculating their average RSS, it is possible to estimate DoA of signals impinging a WSN node equipped with such ESPAR antenna.

Fig. 1. An ESPAR antenna with simplified beam steering, in which top layer metallization is the antenna's ground plane, proposed for WSN nodes in [7] (see text for explanations).

III. RSS-BASED DOA ESTIMATION USING ESPAR ANTENNAS

Because RF transceivers within simple and inexpensive WSN nodes can usually provide RSS values associated with received radio packets, among many DoA estimation algorithms that can be used together with ESPAR antennas, those relying on RSS of RF signals recorded at the antenna output are particularly relevant for WSN applications [7]. Both RSS-based DoA estimations algorithms for ESPAR antennas, namely PPCC that relies on an estimator [5], [7] and recently introduced machine learning approach involving

support vector machine (SVM) classification [13], require a calibration, which has to be performed once in an anechoic chamber before the actual DoA estimation process starts. During the calibration phase, one has to measure twelve ESPAR antenna's radiation patterns in the horizontal plane $\{P(V_{max}^1, \varphi), P(V_{max}^2, \varphi), \dots, P(V_{max}^{12}, \varphi)\}$ for all considered steering vectors $\{V_{max}^1, V_{max}^2, \dots, V_{max}^{12}\}$, and then these radiation patterns are used to create corresponding DoA estimation algorithm.

A. Power Pattern Cross-Correlation (PPCC) method

To perform DoA estimation using PPCC method, one has to calculate cross-correlation coefficient $\Gamma(\varphi)$ [5], which, for the considered ESPAR antenna, can be written as [6]:

$$\Gamma(\varphi) = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{12} (P(V_{max}^n, \varphi) Y(V_{max}^n))}{\sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{12} P(V_{max}^n, \varphi)^2} \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{12} Y(V_{max}^n)^2}} \quad (1)$$

where $\{Y(V_{max}^1), Y(V_{max}^2), \dots, Y(V_{max}^{12})\}$ are RSS values recorded at the antenna output for the corresponding steering vectors during the actual DoA estimation process. Due to the fact that the radiation patterns are measured in an anechoic chamber with an angular step precision $\Delta\varphi$ they can be represented as vectors $\mathbf{p}^n = [p_1^n, p_2^n, \dots, p_I^n]^T$, which values correspond to discretized angles φ that can be written as $\boldsymbol{\varphi} = [\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_I]^T$. Therefore, equation (1) can easily be implemented in a WSN's microcontroller memory as [5]-[7]:

$$\mathbf{g} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{12} (\mathbf{p}^n \circ Y(V_{max}^n))}{\sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{12} (\mathbf{p}^n \circ \mathbf{p}^n)} \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{12} Y(V_{max}^n)^2}} \quad (2)$$

where the Hadamard product \circ is element-wise product of vectors and $\mathbf{g} = [\Gamma(\varphi_1), \Gamma(\varphi_2), \dots, \Gamma(\varphi_I)]^T$ is a vector of length I that contains discretized values of the correlation coefficient $\Gamma(\varphi)$ associated with the appropriate values of φ in the vector $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$. It has been shown [7], that the estimated DoA angle $\hat{\varphi}$ is a value in the vector $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$, which corresponds to the highest value in \mathbf{g} .

B. DoA Estimation Using SVM-Based Classification

The alternative approach to DoA estimation based on measured RSS values $\{Y(V_{max}^1), Y(V_{max}^2), \dots, Y(V_{max}^{12})\}$ has recently been proposed in [13]. Because angles in $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$ are discretized, they can be treated as I different "classes" containing 12 measured radiation patterns for considered steering vectors $\{V_{max}^1, V_{max}^2, \dots, V_{max}^{12}\}$. Therefore, multiclass supervised classification algorithms [17] can be used to find a relation between angle and measured power levels. All considered angles φ_i with corresponding antenna patterns $\mathbf{p}_i = [P(V_{max}^1, \varphi_i), P(V_{max}^2, \varphi_i), \dots, P(V_{max}^{12}, \varphi_i)]$ measured for this angle during the training phase can be written as a training set $D = \{(\mathbf{p}_0, \varphi_0), (\mathbf{p}_1, \varphi_1), \dots, (\mathbf{p}_I, \varphi_I)\}$. In classification approach, power levels \mathbf{p}_i are treated as "features" and a trained classifier will estimate direction-of-arrival $\hat{\varphi}$ by finding a discretized angle φ_i in $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$.

Among many classification algorithms, Support Vector Machine (SVM) was proven to be successful with problems involving unstructured and high dimensional data [18]. The main aim of SVM algorithm is to compute a hyperplane in N -dimensional space (where N is number of features), which effectively separates given points (samples) from each other. This hyperplane can be defined as the following decision boundary [19]:

$$\hat{y} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{when } \mathbf{w}^T \cdot \mathbf{x} + b < 0 \\ 1, & \text{when } \mathbf{w}^T \cdot \mathbf{x} + b \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{w} and b are coefficients of hyperplane obtained during training process and \mathbf{x} represents a point (sample) to be classified. This training process consists of solving optimization problem with given y and \mathbf{x} to compute a margin between given samples in N -dimensional space. The samples that define the margin (lie on its border) are called support vectors. When points are linearly separable, any margin violations can be avoided. Thus, the optimization leads to minimizing the hyperplane coefficients:

$$\underset{\mathbf{w}, b, \zeta}{\text{minimize}} \quad \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{w}^T \cdot \mathbf{w} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{subject to: } t^{(k)}(\mathbf{w}^T \cdot \mathbf{x}^{(k)} + b) \geq 1$$

where $t = \pm 1$ represents one of the binary class and $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$ is a training sample number. However, in practical DoA problems, antenna's radiation patterns are measured at I horizontal angles. It means, that instead of binary classification (3), many binary SVMs has to be used. The "one-versus-rest" approach, proposed to RSS-based DoA estimation in [13], uses I classifiers, which correspond to the binary process repeated at every considered horizontal angle. This approach differs one class against the rest of them and then uses a confidence score (i.e. distance from the boundary) to match appropriate class. Moreover, in case samples cannot be linearly separable, a technique called *kernel trick* can be additionally used [19]. The main idea behind it is to add more dimensions to a given N -dimensional features space by using so called kernel function $\phi(\mathbf{x})$, which operate on an existing feature vector \mathbf{x} . This allows for transformation of the feature vector to the dimension, in which samples can be linearly separable, and expands SVM, so the algorithm can tackle DoA problems [13], [19].

IV. MEASUREMENTS

To verify, how reduced number of radiation patterns influence the performance of DoA estimation relying on ESPAR antennas, we have installed the antenna presented in Fig. 1 in our $11.9 \times 5.6 \times 6.0$ m anechoic chamber on the turntable as shown in Fig. 2. Then, to calibrate both DoA estimation algorithms, we have measured all 12 radiation patterns of the ESPAR antenna at 2.484 GHz with angular step precision $\Delta\varphi = 1^\circ$ in the horizontal direction.

To verify DoA estimation accuracy, a single SDR-based device (NI PXIe-5840), which is a signal generator and a

signal analyzer connected to a dedicated PC controller, in a setup proposed in [8] has been used in the same anechoic chamber. For every RSS measurement, 10 snapshots of 10 dBm 2.484 GHz BPSK test signal were generated by NI PXIe-5840 vector signal generator (VSG). Each time, such test signal have been received by NI PXIe-5840 vector signal analyzer (VSA) connected to ESPAR antenna's output and then additive white Gaussian noise has been added to obtain signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) equal to 20dB. In the performed DoA estimation tests, signal's directions were set by rotating the receiving ESPAR antenna with a discrete angular step equal to 5° in the horizontal plane, which resulted in 72 test directions $\varphi_t \in \{0^\circ, 5^\circ, \dots, 355^\circ\}$. Additionally, for every signal's direction twelve RSS values have been recorded for all the main beam antenna configurations.

DoA estimation errors were calculated using the PPCC algorithm expressed by (2) and SVM algorithm implementation using library for support vector machines (LIBSVM) [14] and Scikit-Learn packet [15]. During the SVM training process the "one-versus-rest" approach have been applied to create I classifiers for all the horizontal angles and Gaussian Radial Based function as the *kernel* function have been used to achieve higher generalization in the DoA classification problem [13].

Fig. 2. Measurement setup used in the experiment (see text for explanations)

Measurement results, shown in Table I, indicate that both algorithms can provide results of the similar accuracy levels when the number of radiation patterns is halved. Additionally, when patterns {1,3,5,7,9,11} are used, the *rms* error obtained from PPCC method drops to 0.95° , while the time required to gather the data is 470.16 ms. Therefore, the results in this case are better than for the algorithm employing all 12 radiation patterns, for which the same time is twice as big and equals to 940.32 ms. When lower, than 6, numbers of radiation patterns are used, one can expect a severe accuracy drop. However, in some WSN applications, e.g. beam steering, the highest possible DoA estimation accuracy might not be necessary. For example, the considered ESPAR antenna has 3 dB beamwidth equal to 73.2° , which means that

DoA estimation results based on only 3 radiation patterns, namely {2,6,10}, that provide 22° (PPCC) or 17° (SVM) precision can also be utilized. If it is the case, the time required to gather the necessary data is 235.08 ms.

TABLE I
DOA ESTIMATION ERRORS CALCULATED FOR REDUCED NUMBER OF ESPAR ANTENNA'S RADIATION PATTERNS USING CONSIDERED RSS-BASED ALGORITHMS (SEE TEXT FOR EXPLANATIONS).

Radiation Patterns Used in DoA Estimation	PPCC		SVM	
	rms	precision	rms	precision
{1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12}	1.24°	5°	0.87°	2°
{1 3 5 7 9 11}	0.95°	5°	1.19°	3°
{2 4 6 8 10 12}	1.49°	6°	1.27°	3°
{1 4 7 10}	13.88°	57°	2.16°	13°
{2 5 8 11}	11.94°	66°	13.42°	70°
{3 6 9 12}	10.47°	53°	3.02°	16°
{1 5 9}	5.21°	43°	5.29°	37°
{2 6 10}	3.97°	22°	2.77°	17°
{3 7 11}	10.41°	48°	5.51°	45°
{4 8 12}	7.07°	34°	4.22°	24°

V. CONCLUSIONS

In the article, we have verified the accuracy of RSS-based DoA estimation algorithms based on values recorded at ESPAR antenna's output port when limited number of radiation patterns are used. Although ESPAR antennas having twelve passive elements and using simplified beam steering are able to provide 12 directional radiation patterns, we have shown, that accurate results can be generated by using only 6 radiation patterns, instead of 12 that are available. It means that the time required for DoA estimation can be reduced from 940.32 ms to 470.16 ms. Additionally, when WSN applications, which does not require accurate DoA estimation results (e.g. beam steering using ESPAR antennas), are considered, it is possible to use only three radiation patterns. In this case, the time required for DoA estimation can further be reduced to 235.08 ms while the available precisions are still applicable in WSN nodes having simple and inexpensive transceivers.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Research leading to these results has received funding from the EU ECSEL Joint Undertaking under grant agreement no. 737459 (project Productive4.0) and from the National Centre for Research and Development on behalf of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education in Poland.

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